

Cos4Env

Training & capacity building resources

Cos4Cloud Services

About the Cos4Env system & user guide

This is a system and user guide to [Cos4Env](#) a service that integrates environmental observations from multiple citizen observatories saving time by providing easier access to a wide environmental data in one place.

Description

Cos4Env is a service that integrates environmental observations from multiple citizen observatories (CO) into one place. This provides easier access for citizen science experts to view and search large numbers of environmental measurements from different sources while interacting with CO communities and contributing to their knowledge.

Cos4Env has been developed by [Bineo Consulting](#) as part of [Cos4Cloud](#), a European Horizon 2020 funded project. The Cos4Cloud project developed [thirteen services](#) boosting citizen science technological services to help increase and improve the quantity and quality of observations.

Cos4Env is one of the three services developed by Bineo. Two are services that combine observations from citizen observatories focused on environmental ([Cos4Env](#)) and biodiversity (Cos4Bio) data which allow experts to spend less time accessing and searching data. The other is the Data Use Notification Service ([DUNS](#)), a service that registers the use of observations downloaded from Cos4Bio and passes info back to the COs where the observations originated from.

Service Coordinator

Cos4Cloud Coordinator

The following content has been provided to help guide users of this service.

WHAT IS COS4ENV?

Cos4Env is an open-source service that integrates environmental observations from multiple citizen observatories in one place, allowing experts to save time in the download process and get access to a wide range of environmental data. With **Cos4Env** citizen science experts can view and search through a wide range of environmental measurements from a single site, interacting with observations and data from different CO communities, and contribute their knowledge.

Observations in **Cos4Env** are from citizen observatories integrated into the service, this includes **Cos4Cloud COs** focused on the environment *OdourCollect* (<https://odourcollect.eu/>) and *CanAirIO* (<https://canair.io/>).

WHO IS THIS SERVICE FOR AND WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS?

Cos4Env is a service that enables COs to integrate environmental observations, it is aimed at expert users or users with knowledge of recording environmental measurements (i.e. odour, air or water quality), who want to collaborate, access data, and provide information on observations added by users on the different COs. Key benefits of this service include:

- Provides a service that aggregates citizen observations in a system that reduces the time citizen science experts spend searching for and downloading environmental data
- Allows users to download observations from one portal which has the capabilities to recognise and notify each observation's authorship in the CO it originates from.
- Enhances the power of citizen observatories providing access to better trained algorithms than databases with only the information of a single observatory.
- Gives visibility to the contribution made by each expert, allowing them to share their profile with information including comments made, searches and downloads.

- Experts can contribute their comments all in one place and once posted in **Cos4Env** this is automatically added on the CO platform the environmental measurement came from. For example, if a citizen science expert comments on an environmental measurement through **Cos4Env** and this is from *OdourCollect*, the user will be informed about the contribution.

HOW DOES IT WORK?

Cos4Env allows citizen science experts to consult information on the environment in one place. It integrates data from multiple COs in one place and unifies information from different observatories in a standardised format, users can also download this data for research, studies or reports etc.

When a CO is integrated into **Cos4Env** observations that appear are linked directly using an API; this data is not stored but available for visualisation or downloading.

From Cos4Env users can:

- Apply different criteria to filter or search for information such as: type, location, citizen observatory or date.
- See the details of a record, make comments.
- See and share user profiles, comments made, and downloads.
- Download environmental variables datasets in a standardised format.

Any validation of observations by experts will always be done through the CO itself, using their established criteria which varies based on the specification of the CO. For example, some algorithms require a certain degree of expertise to validate, but in others several comments of the same register are required. The file of each environmental variable register can be seen by entering the details of each one.

Cos4Env provides easier access to a wide range of data which users can download data in standardised format for research, reports etc. Once logged in users can search the environmental data of interest using multiple criteria, i.e. 'type of environmental measurement': air quality, water quality, temperature, odour, etc Data downloads include information about the host CO, guided by their Terms and Conditions of use.

HOW TO USE COS4ENV – A STEP BY STEP GUIDE

Cos4Env is a service that can be used by environmental COs who would like to integrate their observations. It is also targeted at expert users or users with knowledge of recording environmental measurements: air quality, water quality, temperature, odour, etc who want to collaborate, access data, and provide information on observations from the different COs. This guide is for users of the **Cos4Env** platform.

Citizen observatories developers and leaders interested in integrating their CO environmental observations within **Cos4Env** can request information related to the **Cos4Env** API: contact: info@bineo-consulting.com

01

GO TO THE COS4ENV WEBSITE AND LOG-IN:

Go to the **Cos4Env** website: <https://cos4env.eu/>

To get started select a language of choice and browse the latest observations:

Click login: Log-in access to Cos4Env is via **AUTHENIX**, a Cos4Cloud user authentication service.

For further information about AUTHNENIX go to the website (<https://www.authenix.eu/>). See the Privacy Policy [<https://www.authenix.eu/PrivacyStatement>] and terms of use [<https://www.authenix.eu/TermsOfUse>]

Select the preferred login option.

02

LOG-IN, SET UP A USER PROFILE AND EXPLORE ACTIVITY:

Once logged in go to the user *profile button* and complete the information requested and click *update* to save any changes. **Cos4Env** give visibility to contributions made by each expert, and information about the contributor is made available on comments, as well as details about their activity i.e. searches and downloads.

Explore and view user activity from the Dashboard (<https://cos4env.eu/dashboard>):

03 USE COS4ENV FEATURES:

Cos4Env is a service that allows experts to access environmental observations from multiple citizen observatories in a single place. Features that support this include:

Search and filter observations: find records of environmental information from the citizen observatories integrated into **Cos4Env** by specifying search criteria and applying filters i.e. by location / place name, the CO platform or portal, type of environmental measurement, etc:

Apply other filter or search options to access information: the type of licence applied or the date / timeline. A combination of filters can also be used at the same time.

04

VIEW OBSERVATIONS:

In **Cos4Env** details of environmental observations can be viewed from the map view visible on the front page by clicking on each observation or by opening each observation listed in the results generated from a filter and search action. Observation information can include: code, number of comments date of publication, name of the host CO, coordinates (latitude and longitude), measurements i.e. type and value.

05

SEARCH, VIEW AND DOWNLOAD OBSERVATIONS:

Apply selected filters and search for observations, results can be downloaded as a csv file:

Select the required filter options, for example the CO and environmental measurement recorded i.e. *Portal – OdourCollect* and *Types – Odour Type – Rotten eggs*, as demonstrated in the following examples:

Click SEARCH to generate the results:

Click DOWNLOAD to the right of the screen, select the purpose / reason for downloading, then DOWNLOAD at the bottom of the pop-up menu. A csv file with the data will be generated and saved:

INFORMATION AND FURTHER SUPPORT

Introduction to this Cos4Cloud service: <https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/cos4env/>

Cos4Env help, support and user information: <https://cos4env.eu/en/help>

About Cos4Env: <https://cos4env.eu/en/about>

Contact: info@bineo-consulting.com

Cos4Bio Terms and Conditions: <https://cos4env.eu/en/terms>

Citizen Observatories integration information Cos4Bio API: contact: info@bineo-consulting.com

Get the Cos4Cloud infographic for this service: [Cos4Env infographic](#)

Additional resources: [About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#)

This system and user guide is a training resource for Cos4Env, one of the technological services co-designed by the Cos4Cloud project (<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>). **Title: Cos4Env System and User Guide.** Service Coordinator Bineo Consulting. This guide is one of the Training and Capacity Building resources in the Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub developed by the Open University in collaboration with project partners. Contact: cos4cloud-toolbox@open.ac.uk.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 863463.